

**PARTICIPATION LEVEL OF YOUTH FARMERS IN INCOME
GENERATING ACTIVITIES OF AGRICULTURAL
INTERVENTION PROJECT IN OYO AND ONDO
STATES, NIGERIA**

¹Adeyemi, F. G., ¹Adeyemo, P. A., ¹Adelakun, S. A., ²Bankole, E. M., ³Bankole, J. A.

¹Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomosho, Nigeria,

²Department of Pure and Applied Biology, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomosho, Nigeria

and

³Teaching and Research Farms, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomosho, Nigeria

Abstract:

Poor access to funds and other inputs accounted for the most worrisome bottleneck to youth participation in Agricultural intervention project. The study therefore evaluated the participation level of youth farmers in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project in Oyo and Ondo States, Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was adopted to select a total of three hundred and twenty-nine (329) youth farmers for the study. A structured questionnaire was employed to obtain primary data from respondents. Two sampled t-test was used to analyze the difference between the participation level of youth farmers in income generating activities of Farmers in Oyo and Ondo States. It was revealed that respondents from Oyo State had a mean score of 3.57 for level of youths' participation in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project while respondents from Ondo State had a mean score of 3.22 level of youths' participation in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project. The mean difference between the level of youths' participation in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project scores for Oyo State and Ondo State was found to be 0.35. The standard error of the mean between the Oyo State and Ondo State was found to be 0.137. The mean difference of level of youths' participation in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project score between Oyo and Ondo states youths was found to be significant (F-value = 20.819) and (t-value = 2.560). Based on the findings, it was concluded that youths from Oyo State participated more in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention than youths from Ondo State.

Therefore, this study recommends that youth from Ondo state should participate more in income generating activities like their counterparts from Oyo State.

Keywords: Agriculture, Income Generating Activities, Participation, Youths.

1. Introduction:

Youth have been differently defined by various authors worldwide. Okogun (2004) declared that “youthful period” is the time when a man’s power and attributes are developed to highest potential. It is a period when a man’s strength is at its highest peak. In Nigeria, a youth is described as any person between the age of 18 and 35 years and they make up 80 percent of the total population and constitute about 76 percent of the agricultural labour force (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2017). Anyidoho et. al. (2012) presented the age bracket of youth in some other sub-Sahara African countries as follows: Ghana (15-35), Senegal (15-35), Kenya (15-35 by Kenya’s National youth policy while 18-35 by Kenya Youth Enterprise Development Fund. For the purpose of this study, the definition of youth by the National Youth Development Policies of Nigeria will be adopted.

According to Muthee (2010), youth are not largely involved in agricultural enterprises since agriculture as a career choice is burdened with misperceptions and a lack of information and awareness. This is mostly due to uncompetitive wages, the physical aspects associated with work in the sector and the lack of awareness of what careers in the agricultural sector has to offer. Muthee (2010), further reported that the emergence of petroleum industry as the main foreign exchange, coupled with other socioeconomic restraints has resulted in youth not actively participating in agricultural enterprises. Most of the young people in Nigeria would rather work in an oil company than in the farm which is considered as a dirty and non-rewarding job.

Hypothesis:

H01: There is no significant difference between the participation levels of youths in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project in Oyo and Ondo States.

2. Methods:

The study was carried out in Oyo and Ondo States, South-western geographical zone of Nigeria. The population of the study comprise both male and female youths participating in Agricultural intervention income generating activities in Ondo state in south-western geographical zone of Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select a total of three hundred and twenty-nine (329) youth farmers. Data collection from the respondents was mainly through structured questionnaire. Information contained in the structured questionnaire were based on the objectives of the study.

Data were analyzed using both descriptive (frequency count, percentage, weighted mean score and mean) and two sampled t-test statistics using SPSS version 22.

3. Results and Discussion:

Table 1 shows the summary of t-test analysis of the significance difference between respondents from Ondo State and Oyo State as regards level of youths’ participation in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project.

It was revealed that respondents from Oyo State had a mean score of 3.57 for level of youths' participation in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project while respondents from Ondo State had a mean score of 3.22 level of youths' participation in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project. The mean difference between the level of youths' participation in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project scores for Oyo State and Ondo State was found to be 0.35. The standard error of the mean between the Oyo State and Ondo State was found to be 0.137. The mean difference of level of youths' participation in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project score between Oyo and Ondo states youths was found to be significant (F-value = 20.819) and (t-value = 2.560) which implies that there is variation in the level of youths' participation in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project among the two States. Youths from Oyo State participated more in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention than youths from Ondo State, this can be linked to the reasons for participating in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project which include due to lack of white collars jobs, to ensure food security, and opportunity for input supply and empowerment scheme.

Test of Hypothesis:

The null hypothesis that stated that there is no significant difference between the participation levels of youths in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project in Oyo and Ondo States is hereby rejected. This agrees with the finding of Valerie (2009) that the benefits derived by rural youths from participating in agricultural enterprises include the following: it serves as a source of employment opportunity for the rural youths, it increases their annual income and it increases the living standard of the rural youths.

Table 1. Summary of t-test analysis difference in the level of youth participation in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention project in Oyo and Ondo States (n = 329)

Groups	Mean	Mean difference	t-value	Df	Std. Error difference	F-value
Ondo State	3.22					
		0.35	2.560	327	0.137	20.819
Oyo State	3.57					

Source: Field Survey, 2021

4. Conclusion:

Based on the findings of this study, it was revealed that youths from Oyo State participated more in income generating activities of Agricultural intervention than youths from Ondo State. Therefore, the study recommended that youth from Ondo state should participate more in income generating activities like their counterparts from Oyo State.

5. References:

1. Anyidoho, N. A; Kayuni, H; Ndugu, J; Leavy, J; Sall, M; Tadele, G; Sumberg, J. (2012). Young People and Policy Narratives in Sub-Saharan Africa. Working Paper 032. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/265068750>. Pp. 4-12.
2. Muthee, M. (2010): Hitting the target, missing the point; youth policies and programs in Kenya. Woodrow Wilson International Centre for Scholars, Washington DC. National Poverty Eradication Plan (1999-2015), Government of Kenya. Government Printers. Pg 23-24.
3. National Bureau of Statistics (2017). Labour force statistics (vol.1); unemployment and under employment, Abuja, Nigeria.